

THE LEADERSHIP SKILLS OF SCHOOL HEADS IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY AND SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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The Leadership Skills of School Heads in Public Elementary and Secondary Schools

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine the leadership skills and level of leadership skills of school heads in public Elementary and Secondary schools in the District of San Jacinto. The respondents composed of 10 respondents, 5 of which from the elementary and another 5 are from the secondary schools using convenience sampling technique. A survey questionnaire was utilized and used Leadership Skills Questionnaire (LSQ). Findings revealed that the level of leadership skills of school heads is very high range in administrative skills, interpersonal skills and conceptual skills. In their socio demographic, it shows that most school heads are competent and qualified school leaders. The study also showed that school heads both in elementary and secondary possessed these factors of leadership skills among the three categories, “Filling out forms and working with details comes easily for me” for administrative skills; “Understanding the social fabric of the organization is important to me”, “The key to successful conflict resolution is respecting my opponent”, and “I work hard to find consensus in conflict situations”, for interpersonal skills; “When problems arise, I immediately address them” and “Making strategic plans for my company appeals to me”, for conceptual skills which are all interpreted as high range. It is hoped that the findings will help administrators to design appropriate support to novice school heads in becoming an effective and efficient school leader.

Keywords: *leadership skills, school heads, elementary schools, secondary schools*

Introduction

A leader must necessarily perform well to effectively influence others to advance their selves as well as the society. A leader is someone who has great vision and promising path towards realizing it. According to Prastiawan, A., Gunawan, et. Al., (2020), the leaders refer to school principals, school heads, and supervisors who are effective because they are qualified to accomplish the vision, mission, and goals of the school. Leaders are anticipated to comprehend emerging management paradigms, novel strategies, change leadership, information dynamics, knowledge-driven employee productivity, and self-management prowess (Day et al., Citation2021). According to Bitterová, M., Hašková, A., & PISOŇOVÁ, M. (2014) quality of school leaders and managers is one of the basic factors influencing significantly quality of teaching and learning processes at each level of the system of education. Skills are the capacity to perform tasks based on professional competencies, with observable outcomes.

At school, the school heads are expected to be the highest performing person among his peers. He/ She must ensure that their team has support and needed tools in achieving their common goal. According to Zepeda (2012) strong instructional leadership upholds brilliance and excellence in education. The principal faces greater challenges than the past in carrying out the duties and functions he plays on a daily basis (Komalasari, K., Arafat, Y., & Mulyadi, M. 2020). In the legal mandate of Chapter 1- Governance of Basic Education Section E, School level of Republic Act No. 9155, Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, it is stated that every school or cluster of schools is led by a school head who is selected, trained, supported, monitored, and accountable for the organization and leading of an institutionalized school improvement process at the school level. This mandate directly pointed out how the school head had to perform his duty as the school chief. It is expected that leadership skills will be exercised with the utmost honesty.

The PPSSH was made into a policy through DepEd Order No. 24, 2020, otherwise known as the National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH) which is made to institutionalize it as a public statement of professional accountability for school heads to reflect on and assess their own practice as they aspire for and pursue professional development.

The act further empowers school leaders to direct the teachers and students to achieve quality learning outcomes. Leadership skills play a crucial role in shaping the performance outcomes of school leaders, particularly in the context of public elementary and secondary schools. Several studies have highlighted the significant influence of leadership skills on school performance. Prastiawan et al. (2020) stated that skilled leader can easily lead the school's course effectively. Therefore, effective leadership skills can enhance the quality of education and student outcomes in a school Kilag, O. K. T., Heyrosa-Malbas, M., Ibañez, D. D., Samson, G. A., & Sasan, J. M. (2023). The effectiveness of schools is very much determined by their leaders' performance. Those who can realize the vision and mission of the schools they lead are good school leaders.

Therefore, the researchers aim to identify the leadership skills that school heads possesses both in public elementary and secondary schools in the District of San Jacinto. Maximizing strengths and improving weak spots of schools leaders will bring the best in his/her colleagues as well as the overall performance of the school. And the results will serves as their basis in giving the appropriate support to school heads for the improvement of their leadership skills.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the leadership skills of the school heads both in public Elementary and Secondary schools. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the selected School heads in public Elementary and Secondary schools in the District of San Jacinto?
2. What are the leadership skills possessed by School heads in public Elementary and Secondary Schools in the District of San Jacinto?
3. What is the level of leadership skills of School heads in Elementary and Secondary schools?
4. What are the possible recommendations can be drawn from the study to enhance strong leadership skills among school heads?

Methodology

Research Design

The study is a quantitative research and used descriptive method to obtain the leadership skills of the school heads in both public Elementary and Secondary schools. This is also used to determine the level of leadership skills among school heads. The data gathered was utilized to analyze recommendations to enhance strong leadership skills among School Heads.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 10 School heads in public Elementary and Secondary School in the District of San Jacinto. Five of which were from Elementary and another five from Secondary. This includes Bagahanglad NHS, Emillio Lee Llacer Sr. HS, San Jacinto NHS, Ceasar P. Altarejos Sr. NHS, Bartolabac IS, Leonardo Barrun ES, San Isidro ES, Interior ES, Almiñe ES, and Tutuban ES.

The convenience sampling technique was used in the study. It is a non-probability sampling method where participants are chosen based on their accessibility and convenience. Researchers selected individuals who are readily available and willing to participate in this study.

Instrument

The researchers used Leadership Skills Questionnaire (LSQ) Northouse, P. G. (2013) survey questionnaire checklist in determining the leadership skills of the School Heads. This survey questionnaire is categorized into 3 skills such as the Administrative skills, Interpersonal skills and Conceptual skills.

Procedure

The researchers were self-administered the survey questionnaire to assure that the target respondents receive the checklist. This survey questionnaire is a checklist consists of 18-item test. This questionnaire can be answered in 10-15 minutes that's why the respondents can get it immediately after answering. It can be also retrieved the day after to give respondents time to think it over.

Data Analysis

This descriptive research method used ranking, percentage and averaging in analysing and interpreting the data.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers notified the respondents in advance thru social media flat form using messenger apps before conducting the research. There is also a letter to respondents attached to the survey questionnaires. They answered the survey questionnaire in their most convenient time to deeply relate to each statement. The researchers assured that the data collected from the respondents remained safe and confidential.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Age distribution of respondents*

Age (years)	Frequency		Percentage
	Elementary	Secondary	
30-35	0	1	10
36-40	1	0	10
41-45	0	0	0
46-50	1	0	10
51-55	1	2	30
56-above	2	2	40
Total	5	5	100

Table 1 shows the age distributions of school head respondents wherein majority are within the range of 56 years old above, and that is 40 percent of the total respondents. Also 51-55 years old ranked second highest that got 30 percent in total. This implies that school

heads are more matured adult individuals and possessed wide experiences in life and in their careers.

Table 2. *Distribution of respondents as to Position*

Position	Frequency		Percentage
	Elementary	Secondary	
TI-TIII	0	1	10
HTI-HTIII	4	2	60
PI-PIV	1	2	30
Total	5	5	100

In table 2 result shows that majority of the school heads are under the position of Head teacher I to head teacher III that is 60 percent of the total respondents. This means that they can still improve their acquired position up to the highest position. The higher the position, the greater the school head/leader they become.

Table 3. *Distribution of respondents as to length of service*

Length of Service (years)	Frequency		Percentage
	Elementary	Secondary	
0-5	0	2	20
6-10	2	1	30
11-15	0	2	20
16-20	3	0	30
21-25	0	0	0
26-above	0	0	0
Total	5	5	100

As shown in table 3, as to the distribution in the length of services of school heads in the District of San Jacinto it clearly manifest that 30 percent of the respondents are under 6-10 years. It means that some of them are still novice school head. This implies that they still need to develop their leadership skills thru seminars and trainings. According to Bayar (2016) new principals encounter numerous challenges during their early stages of headship.

Table 4. *Educational attainment distribution*

Educational Attainment	Frequency		Percentage
	Elementary	Secondary	
Bachelor’s degree	0	0	0
Bachelor w/MA/MS/MAEd Units	2	2	40
MA/MS/MAEd Graduate	3	2	50
MA/MS/MAEd Graduate w/EdD Units	0	1	10
EdD Graduate	0	0	0
Total	5	5	100

In the aspect of educational attainment in table 4, results show that 50% of school heads are Masters Graduate, 40% have units in Master’s degree and 10% are master’s graduate with units in PhD doctor of philosophy. This implies that some school heads need to pursue their studies in graduate schools to attain its highest educational background. Pursuing their education is a big help to develop and widen their potential in managing the school effectively. Sepuru and Mohlakwana (2020) added that school principals are expected to demonstrate proficiency when performing leadership and management roles in schools.

Table 5 shows the results gathered about the leadership skills of schools heads both in public elementary and secondary schools. The following skills got the highest average from the three categories of leadership skills, “Filling out forms and working with details comes easily for me” for administrative skills; “Understanding the social fabric of the organization is important to me”, “The key to successful conflict resolution is respecting my opponent”, and “I work hard to find consensus in conflict situations”, for interpersonal skills; “When problems arise, I immediately address them” and “Making strategic plans for my company appeals to me”, for conceptual skills which are all interpreted as high range.

The statement number 4, “Filling out forms and working with details comes easily for me” scored highest in administrative skills that scored an average of 24.5, this means that school heads in elementary and secondary are knowledgeable in dealing with paper works.

Also, these three factors got highest average score of 24.5 under interpersonal skills, “Understanding the social fabric of the organization is important to me”, “The key to successful conflict resolution is respecting my opponent”, and “I work hard to find consensus in conflict situations”, that was interpreted as high range for school heads both in elementary and secondary. This means that school heads are more particular in creating harmonious relationship with their colleagues inside the school. According to Arman, M., et. Al., (2016) school heads will need to consider the types of behavioral activity that can be used within the organization to facilitate a more positive relationship orientation.

For conceptual skills this statements got highest average score of 24.5, “Making strategic plans for my company appeals to me” and

“When problems arise, I immediately address them”, it means that school heads in the District of San Jacinto are goal-oriented they foresee where their organization is going and how to achieve it with the help of the team, the teachers and the whole staff. The conceptual skills of the school heads are important as they allow them to visualize the entire organization and see the big picture as well as the impact of the decision.

Table 5. Leadership skills of School Heads in Elementary and Secondary

Statement	Elementary scores	Secondary scores	Overall (Ave)	*Interpretation
1. I am effective with the detailed aspects of my work.	24	24	24.0	High range
2. I usually know ahead of time how people will respond to a new idea or proposal.	23	22	22.5	High range
3. I am effective at problem solving.	24	23	23.5	High range
4. Filling out forms and working with details comes easily for me.	25	24	24.5	High range
5. Understanding the social fabric of the organization is important to me.	25	24	24.5	High range
6. When problems arise, I immediately address them.	24	25	24.5	High range
7. Managing people and resources is one of my strengths.	23	23	23.0	High range
8. I am able to sense the emotional undercurrents in my group.	21	22	21.5	High range
9. Seeing the big picture comes easily for me.	24	21	22.5	High range
10. In my work, I enjoy responding to people’s requests and concerns.	24	24	24.0	High range
11. I use my emotional energy to motivate others.	23	23	23.0	High range
12. Making strategic plans for my company appeals to me.	25	24	24.5	High range
13. Obtaining and allocating resources is a challenging aspect of my job.	23	23	23.0	High range
14. The key to successful conflict resolution is respecting my opponent.	25	24	24.5	High range
15. I enjoy discussing organizational values and philosophy.	22	24	23.0	High range
16. I am effective at obtaining resources to support our programs.	24	24	24.0	High range
17. I work hard to find consensus in conflict situations.	24	25	24.5	High range
18. I am flexible about making changes in our organization.	23	24	23.5	High range

Legend: Administrative Skills: (1, 4, 7, 10, 13 and 16); Interpersonal Skills (2, 5, 8, 11, 14, and 17); Conceptual Skills: (3, 6, 9, 12, 15 and 18)
 Scoring: *6.00-10.99: very low range; *11.00-15.99: low range; *16.00-20.99: moderate range; *21.00-25.99: high range; *26.00-30.00: very high range

And among these factors of leadership skills statement number 8 got the lowest average score, “I am able to sense the emotional undercurrents in my group”, although interpreted as high range. This statement fall under interpersonal skills, this means that school heads still need to develop and strengthen their emotional intelligences to better understand their colleagues considering their feeling and perspective and to avoid misunderstanding.

Table 6.1. Scores of Leadership skills of School heads in Elementary

Respondents	Administrative Skill	Interpersonal Skill	Conceptual Skill
Elementary	30	30	30
Elementary	30	28	29
Elementary	29	28	28
Elementary	27	27	28
Elementary	27	28	27
Average	28.6	28.2	28.4
*Interpretation	Very high range	Very high range	Very high range

Scoring: *6.00-10.99: very low range; *11.00-15.99: low range; *16.00-20.99: moderate range; *21.00-25.99: high range; *26.00-30.00: very high range

Table 6.2. Scores of Leadership skills of School heads in Secondary

Respondents	Administrative Skill	Interpersonal Skill	Conceptual Skill
Secondary	30	29	29
Secondary	29	28	29
Secondary	29	28	28
Secondary	27	28	27
Secondary	27	27	28
Average	28.4	28.0	28.2
*Interpretations	Very high range	Very high range	Very high range

Scoring: *6.00-10.99: very low range; *11.00-15.99: low range; *16.00-20.99: moderate range; *21.00-25.99: high range; *26.00-30.00: very high range

As shown in table 6a and 6b, the level of leadership skills of School heads in both public Elementary and Secondary schools in the District of San Jacinto are very high range. The average of their Administrative skills, Interpersonal skills and Conceptual skills are above 26.0 which are interpreted as very high range.

This mean that the leadership skills of school heads is excellent but since it does not scored perfect 30, it manifest that there are still aspect of leadership skills that needs to be improve and develop along the way.

Conclusions

Based from the results of the study conducted, this conclusion can be drawn:

In the socio demographic profile of the schools heads majority are quite old and soon be retiring. Most of them are head teachers and render service over a long period of time. Their educational status need to be push so as to pursue their schooling to attain higher academic background and level up their positions.

The school heads possessed very high range of leadership skills in the three categories which is administrative skills, interpersonal skills and conceptual skills. Having varied average scores for the different skills it showed that school heads still needs to equipped their selves with significant experiences and acquire essential trainings to better enhance their skills in leading the school.

The level of leadership skills of school heads in elementary and secondary is also very high range. Both school levels scored very high in the three categories of leadership skills.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

School heads should push through their schooling in graduate schools to level up their position. Also attend seminars and trainings align to leadership skills development for novice leaders.

Organizing regular team building activities can help strengthen relationships and promote teamwork among school staff. This can improve collaboration and efficiency in achieving common goals.

Hosting quarterly open forums among peers provides an opportunity for school heads to listen to their colleagues' needs and address any emerging problems or conflicts. This promotes transparency, encourages dialogue, and fosters a sense of inclusivity within the school leadership.

School heads should also focus on improving their interpersonal skills to better connect and communicate with individuals and groups within their school community. This can facilitate smoother interactions and foster a more supportive environment. Enhance emotional intelligence for consistency of good rapport with one another.

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